

COMPARISON OF PAL2V FILTER AND KALMAN FILTER USED IN MPU6050 ACCELEROMETER GYROSCOPE SENSOR

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Abstract - Many signals exhibit noise as a component that cannot be ignored; thus, a serie of methods are used with the intention of reducing it. This study compares the Kalman Filter and the PAL2V Filter based on Annotated Paraconsistent Logic using data from the MPU6050 gyroscope accelerometer.

Keywords: Kalman Filter; PAL2V; Annotated Paraconsistent Logic; MPU6050; Simulink.

INTRODUCTION

Noise is an undesirable component in signals because it alters the real value of the signal, generating inaccuracies for systems. In many applications, such as centrifugal fans [1], aerodynamics [2], electrical systems [3], among others, this component cannot be ignored for the optimal operation of the system. Therefore, it is necessary for this signal to be filtered.

One method for noise treatment is the Kalman Filter. Commonly used in navigation, it acts as an estimator filter for state-space variables in dynamic systems [4]. In [5], the Kalman Filter was used for noise attenuation in the MPU6050 gyroscope accelerometer.

The Kalman Filter is a well-established technique that was published in 1960. It is one of the most widely used tools for estimating non-measurable states, even with noise, and also serves as an excellent observer, used in navigation, tracking, robotics, and radar control [6].

Another alternative was developed by [7], who created the PAL2V Filter, a signal processing filter using Annotated Paraconsistent Logic. Paraconsistent Logic differs from traditional binary logic by being able to handle contradictory signals and extract contradictions from them [8].

In the PAL2V filter, the cell responsible for contradiction extraction is the PANCLCTX, using the learning factor (F_L) to construct the filter with a simple algorithm. Its output, μ_E , works as a low-pass filter, while μ_{ECT} functions as a high-pass filter. Equations 1 and 2 present the transfer functions of μ_E and μ_{ECT} , respectively [9].

$$\frac{\mu_E(z)}{\mu(z)} = \frac{F_L}{(1 - (1 - F_L)z^{-1})} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\mu_{ECT}(z)}{\mu(z)} = 0,5 \left(\frac{1 - z^{-1}}{(1 - (1 - F_L)z^{-1})} \right) + 0,5 \quad (2)$$

The approach using Paraconsistent Logic has low mathematical complexity, making it especially suitable for embedded systems with computational limitations [10],[11]. However, this approach cannot be applied to multiple-input and multiple-output systems and requires that values be normalized between 0 and 1.

Therefore, in this article, the approach using the Kalman Filter and the PAL2V filter will be compared, both applied to the MPU6050 gyroscope accelerometer.

DEVELOPMENT

The data was obtained from a system composed of the MPU6050 gyroscope accelerometer sensor and the ESP32 microcontroller. The system remained in a static state for 673.5 seconds, with data extracted every 500 milliseconds, generating 1,347 samples from the accelerometer and gyroscope on the X-axis. Figure 1 shows the assembly of the ESP32 with the MPU6050.

Figure 1 – Circuit assembly with the accelerometer and the ESP32

In Annotated Paraconsistent Logic (APL), it is necessary for values to be established in the range of 0 to 1; therefore, normalization was performed, as represented in Equation 3.

$$\frac{x - V_{min}}{V_{max} - V_{min}} \quad (3)$$

Where x is the value to be normalized, and V_{min} and V_{max} are respectively the lowest and highest values of the sampling.

In this study, a comparison between the Kalman Filter and the PAL2V Filter was developed. The parameters Q (process variance matrix) and R (measurement variance matrix) for the Kalman Filter were 1 and 100, respectively [5]. The input value u was obtained empirically, with a value of 0.035 for the accelerometer and 0.02 for the gyroscope values.

The PAL2V Filter API from Simulink was used, cascading three paraconsistent neural cells (PANCLCTX) connected to the output μ_E to filter the input signal, as shown in Figure 2. Tests were conducted by varying the F_L parameter.

Figure 2 – Simulink Diagram

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Figures 3 and 4, it is possible to analyze the simulation of the output signal behavior when altering the F_L parameter from the accelerometer and gyroscope data, respectively. It is noted that the smaller the value, the better the filtering; however, it induces a delay in the response.

Figure 3 – Graph of the behavior of different values for filtering the Accelerometer values on the X-axis

Figure 4 – Graph of the behavior of different F_L values for filtering the Gyroscope values on the X-axis

In Figures 5 and 6 a comparison is made between the approach using the values obtained from the accelerometer and gyroscope, respectively, using APL (μ) with $F_L=0.1$, the Kalman Filter (\hat{y}), and the unfiltered signal (y). It is noted that the Kalman Filter achieved a smaller delay and a more refined signal filtering.

Figure 5 – PANCLCTX (μ) and Kalman Filter (\hat{y}) to the original signal (y) for the accelerometer values on the X-axis

Figure 6 – PANCLCTX (μ) and Kalman Filter (\hat{y}) to the original signal (y) for the gyroscope values on the X-axis

CONCLUSION

In this study, the performances of the PAL2V and Kalman filters were compared, applied to the X-axis data from the accelerometer extracted every 500 milliseconds from the static MPU6050 sensor. Both filters successfully filtered the signal, with the PAL2V filter providing better filtering but with a delay in response.

The PAL2V filter can be automatically adjusted depending on the noise level of the signal (ripple), as noted in [12],[13]. This functionality could be implemented in the future by dynamically adjusting the F_L parameter according to the detected noise level.

Future work will compare the application of these two filters in embedded systems to evaluate the computational cost of each. They will also be compared in dynamic systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] NEISE, Wolfgang. Noise reduction in centrifugal fans: a literature survey. *Journal of sound and vibration*, v. 45, n. 3, p. 375-403, 1976.
- [2] TALOTTE, C. Aerodynamic noise: a critical survey. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, v. 231, n. 3, p. 549-562, 2000.
- [3] OTT, Henry W.; OTT, Henry W. Noise reduction techniques in electronic systems. New York: Wiley, 1988.
- [4] KOWNACKI, Cezary. Optimization approach to adapt Kalman filters for the real-time application of accelerometer and gyroscope signals' filtering. *Digital Signal Processing*, v. 21, n. 1, p. 131-140, 2011.
- [5] ALFIAN, Rio Ikhsan; MA'ARIF, Alfian; SUNARDI, Sunardi. Noise reduction in the accelerometer and gyroscope sensor with the Kalman filter algorithm. *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, v. 2, n. 3, p. 180-189, 2021.
- [6] PÁRAMO-CARRANZA, Luis A. et al. Discrete-time Kalman filter for Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy models. *Evolving Systems*, v. 8, n. 3, p. 211-219, 2017.
- [7] DE CARVALHO, A. et al. A Study of Paraconsistent Artificial Neural Cell of Learning Applied as PAL2v Filter. *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, v. 16, n. 1, p. 202-209, 2018.
- [8] COELHO, Marcelo Saraiva et al. Hybrid PI controller constructed with paraconsistent annotated logic. *Control Engineering Practice*, v. 84, p. 112-124, 2019.
- [9] DE CARVALHO JUNIOR, Arnaldo et al. A comprehensive review on paraconsistent annotated evidential logic: Algorithms, Applications, and Perspectives. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, v. 127, p. 107342, 2024.
- [10] CARVALHO, Arnaldo et al. Paraconsistent state estimator for a Furuta pendulum control. *SN Computer Science*, v. 4, n. 1, p. 29, 2022.
- [11] CARVALHO, Arnaldo et al. (2023). A Paraconsistent Artificial Neural Cell of Learning by Contradiction Extraction (PANCLCTX) with Application Examples. In: Abe, J.M. (eds) *Advances in Applied Logics . Intelligent Systems Reference Library*, vol 243. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-35759-6_5.
- [12] CARVALHO, Arnaldo et al. Paraconsistent State Estimator for a Furuta Pendulum Control. *SN COMPUT. SCI.* 4, 29 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-022-01427-z>.
- [13] CARVALHO, Arnaldo et al. Paraconsistent Logic Approach for Active Noise Reduction. *Journal of Mechatronics Engineering*, vol. 3, issue 1, pag 2-8, 2020. DOI: 10.21439/jme.v3i1.